

A novel preparation of 3,3-dimethylbutyraldehyde via isomerization of 3,3-dimethyl-1-butene epoxide

Alan R. Katritzky^{a*}, Yunfeng Fang^a and Indra Prakash^b

^aCenter for Heterocyclic Compounds, Department of Chemistry, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL 32611-7200, U.S.A.

E-mail : KATRITZKY@CHEM.UFL.EDU Fax : (352)392-9199

^bNutraSweet Synthesis, 699 Wheeliug Rd, Mt. Prospect, IL 60056-1300, U.S.A.

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3,3-Dimethylbutyraldehyde is prepared in a highly economical manner by regioselective isomerization of the title epoxide in the presence of LiTMP.

3,3-Dimethylbutyraldehyde is an important intermediate in the preparation of the sweetener neotame (*N*-[*N*-(3,3-dimethylbutyl)-*L*- α -aspartyl]-*L*-phenylalanine). Neotame is the next generation of non-nutritive sweeteners from the NutraSweet Company and presently awaits approval by the US FDA for general use as a sweetener. Neotame has a sweetness intensity about 8000 times that of sucrose and 30–40 times that of aspartame¹.

In the process development of neotame, large quantities of high quality 3,3-dimethylbutyraldehyde are required. Several methods for the preparation of 3,3-dimethylbutyraldehyde have been reported, including the hydrolysis of 1,1-dichloro-3,3-dimethylbutane², oxidation of 3,3-dimethylbutanol^{3a,b}, ozonolysis of 4,4-dimethyl-1-pentene⁴ and reduction of 3,3-dimethylbutanoyl chloride⁵. However, in regard to cost, none of these methods is satisfactory. We now report a method for preparing this aldehyde which is both economical and specific.

Rearrangements of epoxides to carbonyl compounds have long been known⁶. For example, epoxides have been converted to aldehydes in a regiospecific manner through the use of lithium perchlorate in diethyl ether (LPDE)⁷, however, acyclic terminal olefin epoxides, such as 1,2-epoxyhexane, did not rearrange in the LPDE medium. Yanagisawa *et al.*⁸ reacted various 1,2-epoxyalkanes with lithium 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (LiTMP) to produce the corresponding aldehydes; however, they did not study the reactivity of 1,2-epoxybutanes which are sterically hindered at the carbon alpha to the epoxide ring, such as 3,3-dimethyl-1,2-epoxybutane. More recently, Anderson *et al.*⁹ reported that aryl-substituted epoxides and aliphatic epoxides with a tertiary epoxide carbon underwent a rearrangement in the presence of bismuth(III) oxide perchlorate to give carbonyl compounds, however, no acyclic terminal ole-

fin epoxides were reported to undergo this rearrangement. We now describe the synthesis of 3,3-dimethylbutyraldehyde by regioselective isomerization of the corresponding epoxide in the presence of a basic lithium salt.

Two methods were reported for the preparation of 1,2-epoxy-3,3-dimethylbutane (2): (i) epoxidation of 3,3-dimethyl-1-butene (1) in methylene chloride with peracetic acid at 0° for 14 days to produce 2 in low yield (19%)¹⁰, and (ii) reduction of 1-bromo-3,3-dimethylbutan-2-one with sodium borohydride to yield the corresponding bromo alcohol, which upon the treatment with potassium hydroxide gave epoxide 2 in 37% overall yield¹¹. Magnesium monoperoxyphthalate hexahydrate (MMPP), a recently developed peracid derivative, is non-shock-sensitive and non-deflagrating¹², and thus is safer to use in both small- and large-scale operations as well as cheaper than *m*-CPBA. We investigated the epoxidation of 3,3-dimethylbutene (1) with MMPP using various solvent systems. Epoxidation of 1 in aqueous isopropanol afforded after usual work-up the crude product which distilled to give 1,2-epoxy-3,3-dimethylbutane (2) in 50% yield.

The isomerization of 2 failed to provide the desired aldehyde 3 in an acceptable yield in the presence of boron trifluoride etherate, mineral acids, or upon heating in a sealed tube, or with LiBr/Al₂O₃ catalysis. However, the use of lithium 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (LiTMP) induced the isomerization and the desired aldehyde 3 was isolated as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (4) in 60% yield.

In conclusion, we have developed an effective method to prepare 3,3-dimethylbutyraldehyde, a precursor to neotame. The method we demonstrated here allows for the preparation of 3,3-dimethylbutyraldehyde in a reproducible and highly economical manner so that the use of this aldehyde in the preparation of a sweetener derived from aspartame becomes commercially practicable.

Experimental

1,2-Epoxy-3,3-dimethylbutane (2): A solution of magnesium monoporphthalate hexahydrate (31.5 mmol) in H₂O (75 ml) was added to a solution of 3,3-dimethylbutene (1; 52.5 mmol) in *i*-PrOH (75 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h. The mixture was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 50 ml) and the combined organic phase was washed with a saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO₃, H₂O and dried over MgSO₄. After confirming the absence of peroxide, the mixture was subjected to distillation to give 1,2-epoxy-3,3-dimethylbutane in 50% yield, b.p. 94–96°; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (TMS) 0.92 (9H, s), 2.59 (1H, dd, *J* 4.7, 2.9 Hz), 2.63 (1H, dd, *J* 4.7, 4.1 Hz), 2.73 (1H, dd, *J* 4.1, 2.9 Hz); ¹³C NMR δ 25.5, 30.5, 44.0, 60.0.

Dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative of 3,3-dimethylbutyraldehyde (4): To a solution of 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (4.06 g, 28.75 mmol) in THF (57.5 ml), a solution of *n*-BuLi in cyclohexane (2 *M*; 14.38 ml, 28.75 mmol) was added dropwise at 0° under argon atmosphere. After stirring for about 30 min, a solution of 3,3-dimethyl-1,2-epoxybutane (2; 1.47 g, 11.5 mmol) in THF (11.5 ml) was added at 20° and the reaction mixture was stirred at this

temperature for another 15 h. The mixture was treated with a saturated aqueous ammonium chloride solution under nitrogen at 20° and extracted with Et₂O. The Et₂O layer was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and filtered. In a separate flask, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP, 4.9 g) was suspended in methanol (98 ml) and concentrated sulfuric acid (7.8 ml) was added cautiously. The solution was filtered and added to the above Et₂O solution. The mixture was concentrated to 60 ml by removing the solvent under reduced pressure and then water was added. The organic layer was separated, and the aqueous layer was extracted with Et₂O (2 × 40 ml). The combined organic layers were dried over anhydrous MgSO₄, then filtered and the filtrate was concentrated to dryness. The crude compound was purified by column chromatography on silica gel using chloroform/hexane (4 : 1) as an eluent to give an orange solid (1.9 g, 60%), m.p. 149–151° (Found : C, 51.32; H, 5.71; N, 19.89. C₁₂H₁₆N₄O₄ calcd. for : C, 51.42; H, 5.75; N, 19.99%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (TMS) 1.04 (9H, s), 2.31 (2H, d), 7.62 (1H, t), 7.93 (1H, d), 8.27 (1H, dd), 9.10 (1H, s), 11.06 (1H, s).

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